

Proposed Discovery of Perattian Thunderbolt of the Gods Strike Location in Versailles, KY

Comparison of Predicted Models and LiDAR scans of Big Sink location in Woodford County; Addendum for Plasmaglyphs and the Megafauna Extinction

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ABSTRACT

In the previous work¹, the author wrote in four parts a prediction of a new vector for megafauna extinction, or at least part that no one has discussed for lack of putting stock into Native testimony: the thunderbolts of the gods. In particular the step potential-voltage provided by extremely large thunderbolts. However, despite reliable prediction and simulation by Dr. Anthony Peratt, no perfect 56-rayed crater site with arc-discharge formation had been located. The author made calculations which were verified by Dr. Peratt's own work. In this work the author presents just such a perfect specimen which, as noted in the aforementioned work, is impossible to be an astrobleme for lack of a bow-shock formation. Furthermore in this work the author presents EMF survey for a nearby located c-henge mound which has the hallmark signs of crater-rim discharge. The EMF survey confirms the hypothesis rather than disproves it, but it opens up other interesting queries, as well. Finally, the author recounts the prediction also made that the Carolina Bays could not possibly be ice impact errata given their various vectors of origin. The news of the Greenland impact has confirmed the author's predictions, and shown very clearly that the evidence disfavors a single comet impact event to achieve the selective but wide extinction required for the Ice Age Megafauna.

Keywords: Big Sink - vajra - megafauna extinction - Greenland crater - Mt. Horeb - EMF

¹ [16]

Synopsis

In the author's landmark paper, "Plasma Petroglyphs (plasmaglyphs), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction,"² the author made five assertions which were new to the megafauna debate:

1. That in the observation of aboriginal North American (and worldwide) glyphs, implicit biases against pre-Christian sciences were manifest through simplistic, but illogical deductions about the meaning of glyphs. That this is typified by the asymmetric "turkey glyph," Eagle mound, and Alligator mound.³ Subsequent discovery by the author in "Great Pyramids of Kentucky"⁴ revealed another such mega-glyph that typified the asymmetric behaviors, but it has not been studied due to site-access restrictions.⁵
2. That in the discussion of megafauna extinction vectors, the mainstream proposition has been made illogically and with racial prejudice. But that the alternative "mainstreamed" vector - a comet strike to ice in Michigan - was incorrect. The author provided a debunking of the Carolina Bays as a single event from a single vector,⁶ and possibly even as an impact cratering.⁷ Subsequent sciences have confirmed the author: findings in Greenland⁸, and calculations of megatsunamis relating to Greenland⁹ have provided better evidence in the author's opinion.
3. The author debunked the comet alone hypothesis on the basis of power levels, melt times, and concepts of biological survival (chiefly the fact that the event was not allowed to be powerful enough to cause widespread extinction **selectively**.¹⁰)
4. The author provided a new vector which has been mentioned only in glancing descriptions by the Talbott-Thornhill et al... camp: Step Potential/Voltage. The author then calculated various magnitudes for the thunderbolts:
 - a. Using a classical Maxwellian electric model, between two planar surfaces.¹¹
 - b. Using MHD derived Jupiter-Io models, and lightning safety standards and spherical calculations.
5. The author provided a concrete culprit for this model: the moon, based upon surface evidence from the moon¹², and upon mythic testimony from Native American tribes and the Enuma Elish.¹³

In the short interim from the publishing date, new data has emerged which provides even more clarity to the subject. The author has reviewed another work from Dr. Peratt which places a reasonable constraint upon the thunderbolts, as well as a visual guide. In that time the author has re-examined the Big Sink scans, and verified Peratt's predictions.

In this paper, measurements of the local C-henge at nearby Mt. Horeb will be made. Comparisons of new calculations based upon the latest SAFIRE data¹⁴ with the classical and MHD models with Peratt 3D

² [14]

³ Ibid. pp. 38-46

⁴ <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Great-Pyramids-of-Kentucky>

⁵ Literally on a top-secret classification federal property: the Bluegrass Army Depot. See the paper for LiDAR scans.

⁶ Ibid. Pp. 16-18

⁷ Ibid. pp. 20-21

⁸ <https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/12941>

⁹

https://www.academia.edu/37958235/Sinking_of_Atlantis_by_Marduk_in_9577_BC_Part_4_Destruction_from_the_flood?fbclid=IwAR1dYF05Jb_54hPoaL0Xlm1G8ZDN_n75s1LdS9rVPCDQ80p8pamPxfDxTkU

¹⁰ Ibid. multiple

¹¹ This calculation will be re-performed herein using new SAFIRE data of 8000 V/m permittivity breakdown, instead of 20 MV/m as cited in author's previous work.

¹² Ibid. Appendix B - M Plates, pp. 159-176

¹³ Ibid. pp. 72-77

¹⁴ <https://youtu.be/5IAiMpmGx-M>

simulations will be made to determine viability for continuing study. Also a short discussion of the problems of the Greenland extinction genesis will be discussed using global flood maps, as well as logical thought experiments.

I :: Thunderbolts Revisited

In Peratt & Yao (2008)¹⁵, two important distinctions that are jejune to this paper were made, which the author did not have *on-hand* in the previous publishing¹⁶:

1. *“Experimentally, the tendency for very intense charged particle beams flowing along a magnetic field to ‘hollow’ into a thin cylinder [5] then filament **into 56 currents** is a characteristic of the plasma produced in multi-terawatt pulse-power facilities [6, 7]. Both experiment and three-dimensional PIC simulations verify this phenomenon. For example, interactions between various numbers of current filaments as a source of electromagnetic radiation sources have been studied.”¹⁷ (emphasis added)*

Figure 1: Thunderbolt Simulation; credit:: Peratt et al...¹⁸

2. *“An estimate for the currents in an intense aurora can be obtained from [12]. For a strong circular aurora of diameter 5000 km, the **total current is about 7 MA.** If this pertains to **28 filaments, each filament conducts 250 kA.** Hence, the Bennett pinch criteria [1] are satisfied, and the currents remain as pinched filaments. A thousand-fold increase in current in Gold’s catastrophic scenario is 7 GA, or for 28 filaments, 250 MA carried by each filament. When reduced to four filaments, **each conducts 1.75 GA.**”¹⁹ (emphasis added)*

This is very useful data, which stems from observations at the Orinoco complex of petroglyphs, which are probably excellent mirrors (and taken as such) for the Ohio River Valley events.

Regarding the first statement, the author compared the simulation (Figure 1, created by using aboriginal art and stratigraphy) with the Big Sink LiDAR site (Figure 2), and found the order of magnitude required of 56 filaments. See Figure 3.

Figure 2 - Big Sink, credit; KY From Above 5FT DEM; reads 1,819 m diameter

¹⁵ https://plasmauniverse.info/downloads-petros/Peratt&YaoAurora-PrehistoryPhys-Scr-T131_2008c.pdf

¹⁶ This is actually important because it provides an ‘acid-test’ of hypothesis 4 from the Synopsis

¹⁷ P. 3

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XadqnsNFjoo>

¹⁹ P. 10

Figure 3 - Stars representing proposed strike locations; assumption is that one stroke will be downward, and the neighbor a return stroke, or a proposed yin yang shape of strokes. Count: 56 stars; credit: author

Regarding the total current being 7 MA, this would propose each bolt representing ~ 125 kA. Assuming the Mt. Horeb site (Figure 4-6) is a multi-stroke (hence the crater-rim discharge) discharge that branched off the previous structure or just after the event, the site would represent 125 kA, but multiplied perhaps across a full length of lightning stroke, which can last ~2.1s. It may last 3x as long as this, but the 2.1 will be used for the calculations in Table 3. Ratios of the diameters in Mt. Horeb will be compared with crater sizes (avg of 10) from Figure 2.

Figure 4 (far- left) - 74.3 m diameter

Figure 5 (left) - 50.1 center mound diameter

Figure 6 (bottom-right) - 10.1 m gap for discharge rim diameter

It is already very clear that the Mt. Horeb site has been maintained by the native population. The author proposes it was restored in the Allegewi (“Adena”²⁰) period, ~600 BCE - 200 CE for its convenient opening, which reflected the worldwide motif of the Paradise Island or Cosmic Mountain atop the Cosmic Pole²¹. But in this case the opening happens to point **towards the Big Sink**. See Figure 7:

Figure 6 - 20.8 km gap from opening of Mt. Horeb mound to center Big Sink “astrobleme”²²

Using 30 km as a minimum height, because of the proposed changes currently present in our atmosphere at that elevation in conductivity (and so a minimum height), and 250-1000km for a medium to maximum altitude as proposed in Peratt & Yao, this represents the angles shown in Table 1 for deviation, using $\tan(20\text{km}/\text{height}) * 180/\pi$.

²⁰ “Thus Allegheny seems most likely to have meant ‘fine river’ in the language of the Delawares, but they later told a story of a mythical tribe called the Allegewi who had lived on that river until defeated by the all-conquering Delawares. More often, when a common name became meaningless, the Indians, like other people, merely accepted it—“Just a name!” [sic] <https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.111746>

Adena is a racist term, as it is applied because the site of a mound removed by owner (who hired archaeologists to do it) who was named Adena. It is not what the People called themselves, or their ancients.

²¹ See “Saturn Myth,” by D. Talbott or [7] by author.

²² Debunked as Astrobleme by author, Ibid. pp. 19

Table 1 - Angle of Deviation

<i>30km</i>	<i>250km</i>	<i>1000km</i>	<i>Mean</i>
45.1°	4.6°	1.1°	16.9°

In the calculation of Peratt's Vajra powers, to compare with our own, we will need a voltage or tension.

Utilizing the standard breakdown voltages in air, the same heights as in Table 1 yield these arc-voltages.²³

Table 2 - Voltage and Energy Calculations for Perattian Heights

	<i>30km</i>	<i>250km</i>	<i>1000km</i>	<i>Mean</i>
h (m)	3.00E+05	2.50E+05	1.00E+06	5.17E+05
C (F)	2.66E-09	2.21E-09	8.85E-09	4.57E-09
e (F/m) ²⁴	1.26E-06	1.26E-06	1.26E-06	1.26E-06
V= 3Mv/m*d	9.00E+11	7.50E+11	3.00E+12	1.55E+12
E (j)	3.39E+15	2.83E+15	1.13E+16	5.85E+15
E (kC)	8.11E+11	6.76E+11	2.70E+12	1.40E+12
Lightning Bolts	6.79E+05	5.66E+05	2.26E+06	1.17E+06
Adjusting Up (Gold's model)	3.39E+18	2.83E+18	1.13E+19	5.85E+18
E (kC)	8.11E+14	6.76E+14	2.70E+15	1.40E+15
Lightning Bolts	6.79E+08	5.66E+08	2.26E+09	1.17E+09

The voltages (shown in bold), are quite high, however they are usefully averaged in the GV range, which is not unreasonable. The Gold's model adjustment is mentioned in Peratt's paper and is an increase of 3 orders, in case of supernova induced flares (so 7 MA becomes 7 GA, as discussed in the above quote).

According to this constraint, we can say that the typical Perattian Vajra is the size of power on the order of 1.1 mega to giga lightning bolts. This seems reasonable, but as mentioned in a previous paper by the author, humans tend towards the word billions as a limit merely because of biological limit in the brain. Theoretically this standard may be either too small or too large. The author thinks, based on the MHD calculations, it may be too high. But that is only because we are comparing it with the Io-Jupiter **steady state** connection.²⁵

Still, we will continue forward with the power calculations in Table 3

²³ <http://bit.ly/2Qd9ffy> for Spreadsheet

²⁴ Though conductivity will change for each, it is a bit complex for our purposes. Sometimes conductivity decreases and sometimes increases with height, depending on the properties of the particular shell. So, for convenience of comparison we simply use the permittivity of air at 1.26×10^{-6} and for the breakdown of air, 3MV/m. Both are found with google.

²⁵ Ibid. Table 11 & 12, pp. 114-115

Table 3 - Perattian Vajra Power Calculations

	56	28	4	1_s	1_m	1M_s	56_m
I (A)	1.25E+05	2.50E+05	1.75E+06	7.00E+06	1.75E+06	7.00E+09	2.50E+05
V	1.55E+12	1.55E+12	1.55E+12	1.55E+12	7.50E+11	3.00E+12	1.55E+12
P (W)	1.94E+17	3.88E+17	2.71E+18	1.09E+19	1.31E+18	2.10E+22	3.88E+17
t (s)	3.00E-01	3.00E-01	3.00E-01	3.00E-01	2.10E+00	3.00E-01	2.10E+00
EP (W/s)	6.46E+17	1.29E+18	9.04E+18	3.62E+19	6.25E+17	7.00E+22	1.85E+17

For the single strokes, a time of 0.3s was used²⁶, and for the multiple strokes, 2.1s was used. 1M_s represents the Gold’s model single stroke for Big Sink. 56_m and 1_m utilize different voltage levels to play with the idea that the voltage will drop somewhat as charge is transferred. For 1_m the 250km height is used, and for 56_m the average height is used. There are many possible permutations and they can’t all be displayed here. For the amperage for each either the 4 stroke or the 28 stroke (dual channel for 56_m) was used.

From the other paper, the author previously wrote,

“Comparing Table 10 and 11, we see that the voltages hover from 10⁻³ to 10⁴ higher in Table 11. The avg expected voltage to soil is 10⁻¹ than table 10. So the delivery power is expected to be about an order of magnitude smaller than in table 10, not 10⁻³. Nevertheless, within reasonability, we are arriving at the “understanding” of what we are dealing with. That is to say from 1.88 exa-watts to 7.5 yotta-watts, with an expected avg of 2.5 zetta-watts, and a assumed limitation of 42.3 exa-watts.

The average lightning stroke, as per Dwyer & Uman, lasts about 20-30 microseconds. We are assuming here that the Vajras are behaving similarly, although we have previously stated they won’t, and certain sites demonstrate reliable geophysical evidence of prolonged return strokes and charge pumping (to saturation). However, to establish conservative boundaries (because the upper end cannot be known), we will use the 30 microsecond value to calculate, again, the joules and kC. Note - the energy released in Bikini H-bomb was 8 M-ton TNT or 8 x 10⁶ x 4.184 x 10⁹ j/ton = 3.3472E+16 j

It’s important not to get hung up on the sigfigs because actual values are incalculable without in situ measurement, which is both impossible and unlikely. It’d be deadly at any rate.

*So we see that at the lower boundary, such as a small strike site, we can expect a vajra to be worth 113 or so lightning bolts, while at the upper end, possibly 450 billion bolts, with an average of about **150-250 thousand bolts of typical lightning.**”²⁷*

Based on Table 2, Perattian vajras (mean) are 484% larger than the MHD mean calculated by the author! So it can be said that the previous estimations were:

1. Conservative enough (especially when reduced by 10⁻³!)
2. Based in some type of reality, even if the arc discharge Peratt proposes is solar-induced in the ionosphere²⁸, instead of a discharge from moon to Earth.

²⁶ Ibid. Table 9 shows all previous assumptions made. Here 0.3s is used as a method of lengthening the stroke time to assumed length of stroke time. 30 micro sec = 0.000030 s so we’re talking 10⁴ more seconds. Let this new assumption advise the reader about the power changes and setting “reasonable” maximums and minimums.

²⁷ Ibid. 115-116

²⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0cDWbgFjCDc>

3. Needing to be increased for the Step Potential ranges, or at least compared with Perattian models, the author wants to again note that the energy calculations in Table 2 result in numbers similar, although a magnitude smaller (17.5%), than the Bikini H Bomb. If Gold's model prevails, then it would be about 17,462 H Bombs.

Now what of the modifications of the Moon-origin model, where the permittivity is as low as 8000 V/m? Can the great distance create comparable levels for the Velikovskian thunderbolt in a classical Maxwellian mode?

Table 4 - Velikovskian-Maxwellian Vajra at Various Distances to Moon

	Full distance	½ distance	⅓ distance	¼ distance
<i>d (m)</i>	3.84E+08	1.92E+08	1.28E+08	9.61E+07
<i>C (F)</i>	3.40E-06	1.70E-06	1.13E-06	8.51E-07
<i>e (F/m)</i>	1.31E+00	3.27E-01	1.45E-01	8.18E-02
<i>V= 8000v/m*d</i>	3.08E+12	1.54E+12	1.03E+12	7.69E+11
<i>E (j)</i>	3.22E+19	4.02E+18	1.19E+18	5.03E+17
<i>E (kC)</i>	7.68E+15	9.61E+14	2.84E+14	1.20E+14
<i>Lightning Bolts</i>	6.43E+09	8.04E+08	2.37E+08	1.01E+08
<i># Vajra to melt Antarctica</i>	2.12E-02	2.65E-03	7.84E-04	3.32E-04
<i>Adjusting down</i>	3.22E+16	4.02E+15	1.19E+15	5.03E+14
<i>E (kC)</i>	7.68E+12	9.61E+11	2.84E+11	1.20E+11
<i>Lightning Bolts</i>	6.43E+06	8.04E+05	2.37E+05	1.01E+05
<i># Vajra to melt Antarctica</i>	2.12E-05	2.65E-06	7.84E-07	3.32E-07
	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Limited
<i>V</i>	1.00E+06	1.00E+08	5.00E+07	2.00E+05
<i>I</i>	2.50E+05	5.00E+08	5.00E+06	6.50E+05
<i>R (space)</i>	4.00E+00	2.00E-01	1.00E+01	3.08E-01
<i>R (soil)</i>	3.00E+07	3.00E+10	1.00E+08	1.00E+08
<i>V (discharge)</i>	7.50E+12	1.50E+19	5.00E+14	6.50E+13
<i>P (V*I)/1000=kW</i>	1.88E+15	7.50E+24	2.50E+18	4.23E+16
<i>joules in .3*10^-6 s</i>	5.63E+11	2.25E+21	7.50E+14	1.27E+13
<i>E (kC)</i>	1.34E+08	5.38E+17	1.79E+11	3.03E+09
<i>Lightning Bolts</i>	1.13E+02	4.50E+11	1.50E+05	2.54E+03
<i>Upper Boundary (j)</i>	5.63E+15	2.25E+25	7.50E+18	1.27E+17
<i>Lower Boundary (j)</i>	5.63E+08	2.25E+18	7.50E+11	1.27E+10
<i>Avg Limit (j)</i>	5.63E+10	2.25E+20	7.50E+13	1.27E+12

The above table replicates the various tables used in the previous paper, but with a smaller breakdown voltage. This is highly tentative, as the actual *new vacuum breakdown* has not been officially released. However, a cross-examination yields that numbers are within similar boundaries as per the Perattian and MHD models, except they are higher. Again, comparing lightning bolts (5Gj ea), we see 101 million bolts or about 3 orders bigger than the MHD and 2 orders bigger than Perattian vajra. In H-bombs, the energy is one to three orders larger at 10^{17-19} j. What is actually discharged into the soil, however, in 30 microseconds is lower than an H-bomb by about 3 orders of magnitude. That indicates that it was prudent, after all, of the author to do the lightning safety calculations in the previous work to have an upper and lower boundary.²⁹

II :: Mt. Horeb Sample of Remnant

Although the remnant site is not likely to represent the charge situation from the ancient days, the author wanted to conduct a EMF study (a brief one), using analog measuring devices, of the Mt. Horeb site, and develop a profile, for interest.

Naturally the site **is contaminated** with human traffic, rain, 2k-4k years of erosion, radiation, and lightning strikes. However, the site is potentially interesting, nevertheless. The Big Sink is both too large and on private land, and this makes it fairly difficult to study. Its average crater size, based on 10 random samples, is 46.8 m diameter. Mt. Horeb is 50m in diameter from moat center to moat center, or 74.3 if you use the outer edge of the outer rim. The largest Big Sink crater is ~ 76.5 m, so Mt. Horeb would *just fit* inside of 1 single stroke. However, as mentioned it has a crater rim discharge (as does the largest ones at Big Sink).

Figure 7 - Crater Rim Discharge in a single crater at Big Sink³⁰; credit: author

²⁹ Ibid. pp. 123-125

³⁰ In the previous work the author used Jephtha Knob and Middleboro crater to demonstrate how Big Sink lacks the necessary features of an impact crater. Geologists, similarly cannot find the impact fracturing and the “karst” like sinking is a bit too circular all in all for a typical cave geology. Here we can see that the single craters, which in person appear as

What if the Mt. Horeb C-henge mound site was created by a similar process, or at a minimum inspired by it? What type of EMF would we expect in either case? For the case of the site being the result of crater rim discharge machining around an anode mound, we would expect a strong positive response in the center, and a weak electron presence, although not necessarily absent. Ideally, there should be a strong charge presence at the neck of the mound, where the alleged discharge would have happened, while at the moat there should not generally be a strong field presence.

The survey was carried out April 27, 2019, which was a sunny morning that turned overcast after lunch. It was concluded previous to any rainy conditions. It would have been ideal to conduct at night with a robot, but this is not possible due to the circumstances surrounding use of the park and available equipment.

Nevertheless, two different electromagnetometers were used:

1. Trifield 100XE E/B analog meter with no grounding, and no positive reading
2. IOD40 E-meter, also analog, with dampening, +/- capable, grounding capable (not used), extending antenna, and sensitivity adjustment.
 - a. This device was very sensitive. A baseline had to be set to 1+/- and even then had to be cross-checked multiple times to make sure the device was performing correctly. It is sensitive enough to react to the slightest motion, including laughing, talking, deep breathing, etc...

It goes without saying that all other electronics were put far away from the surveying, and that even still the results cannot be considered definitive, but only indicative of need for further study. To conduct the study the author overlaid a 100 pt grid on the LiDAR scan (5ft DEM) of the site:

depressions, are not at all impacts, evidenced from a lack of bow shock on each and the whole. Also, how would an impact split into 56 or so smaller chunks to perfectly impact the site? It is statistically impossible.

Figure 8 - Mt. Horeb Survey Grid (dimensions provided in Table 5)

Table 5 - Important Dimensional Information for Mt Horeb (in feet and inches)

Vector	Length or Radius	Inner slope @ Peak	Outer slope @ Peak
A6J6	224'	28'	
G6I6	54'8"		
E1E10	200'		24'
E3E1 ½	50'		
E6C4	100'		
E6H3 ½	111'		
E6G8	116'		
E6B/C8 ½	100'		
B7A6 and A6B5	24'		

B7B5 just the neck	35'		
B4 and C5		28'	28'
D2 and E3		30'	33'
G6 and I6		28'	32'
F8 and G9		26'	33'
D8 and D9		24'	28'

Feet and inches acquired from 100 ft. tape, errors +/- 1 foot should be assumed due to human error.

The results for the Trifield³¹ and IOD40³² E fields were different, as it is suspected that the Trifield is perhaps averaging the +/- characteristics, or the results aren't reliable for some reason. However, the 3D mesh plots tell the expected story:

³¹ <http://bit.ly/2IP3LHE>

³² <http://bit.ly/2DDIa1L>

Trifield Ef

Figure 9 - Trifield E measurements, 1.6 V/m max; note graph is X flipped from Figure 8

Trifield Bf

Figure 10 - Trifield Magnetic plot, 2.5 mG max along neck to center

Electron Field

Figure 11 - IOD40 negative measurement, max 5 V/m

Proton Field

Figure 12 - IOD40 positive measurement, max 5 V/m; note strong anode presence

Please note that the B-field measurements were expected, as the site had been visited before and these results were somewhat observed along the neck and particularly strong at B5-6 and in the center, where pulsing changes in the magnetometer were found that exceeded 5 mG routinely.

Participating in this survey was another plasma/aerospace engineer who works for Rolls Royce Engineering, Eric Wilson. It was under his suggestion that the site was behaving like a loop antenna with a 12+” plasma electric cloud hovering over the outer rim, so the author ran some simulations on the antenna with low wattage ($\frac{1}{4}$ W), just to see the simulation:

Several runs determined that 300kHz range (plasma waveform frequencies) were best for such a massive (628') diameter. The increased width of the ring from 12” to 72” actually increased efficiency from 84% to 98%!!

“Antenna efficiency: 98% (-0.1 dB below 100%)

Antenna bandwidth: 0.170 kHz

Tuning Capacitance: 608 pF

Capacitor voltage: 620 volts RMS

Resonant circulating current: 0.711 A

Radiation resistance: 0.242 ohms

Loss Resistance: 0.005 ohms

Inductance: 463 microhenrys

Inductive Reactance: 872 ohms

Quality Factor (Q): 1,764

Distributed capacity: 515 pF

Antenna "circumference": 628 feet

Side

length:

78.5 feet

Antenna

diameter:

189.5 feet

Figure 13 - Loop Antenna Simulation

Comments:

The specified conductor length of 628 feet is OK.

Conductor length should be between 398 and 796 feet at the specified frequency of .3 MHz.

For highest efficiency, the conductor length for a small transmitting loop antenna should be greater than $\frac{1}{8}$ wavelength (greater than about 398 feet at the specified frequency of .3 MHz).

To avoid self-resonance, the conductor length for a small transmitting loop antenna should be less than $\frac{1}{4}$ wavelength (less than about 796 feet at the specified frequency of .3 MHz).

Input Values:

Length of conductor: 628 feet

Diameter of conductor: 72 inches

Frequency: 0.3 MHz

Transmitter power: 0.25 watts³³

³³ <http://www.66pacific.com/calculators/small-transmitting-loop-antenna-calculator.aspx>

Separately, another engineer, Neil Thompson has suggested that a form of loop capacitance gathers charges at the neck, and that the charges are forced away from the East end (H/J columns), as they seek to approach each other but the loop is broken at the neck. Meanwhile, the flat charge accumulating panel in the center, with its rocks, continues to collect and/or dissipate charges to create an equalized AC circuit. Please note that the B-field anomalies in the E/F columns that extend into the rim may be either the Earth's magnetics or the presence of a limestone spring deep underground which was found to emerge 40 feet below at the creek.

It is important to also note that there are numerous (perhaps a dozen) trees located on the mound, which may act as receiver antennas that could interfere with measurements. Where possible, measurements were aimed away from them with the IOD40, along grid lines, but generally towards the center.

Discussion

While the survey cannot be considered determinative, it is highly indicative of the hypothesis thus proposed, or at a very minimum that the Native Allegewi had thus designed a very impressive technological apparatus. Every person, regardless of experience with energetics and traditional systems, felt unique energy presence at the neck from A6 to the center of the circle. What makes this seem even more *designed* and deepens the mystery is that when historian Alan Wilson visited the site, he recognized the Welsh pattern, and predicted a burial mound a mile from the neck. Indeed at 1.45 miles, a Roman league away, such a mound exists:

Figure 14 - Burial Mound in relation to Mt. Horeb earthworks; credit: KFA

Either way, designed/engineered energetics, or discovered and maintained it for thousands of years since the strike first occurred - if indeed it is a crater rim discharge site, and if related to Big Sink. The presence of EMF energetics in a palpable form would justify a religious experience that has hitherto been ignored as a possible reality and probable fact of native Shamanistic socio-religious experience. This lends much credit to the testimony of the Delaware chief, after all!³⁴

³⁴ "In Search of Ice Age Americans," K. Tankersley, and [16]

III :: Greenland, Comets, Megatsunamis, and Continental Crust Displacement

As mentioned in the Synopsis, Greenland has yielded a comet or asteroid impact crater, which is something tangible, and clearly much better than proposing a strike site that disappears once it melts. However, there is a problem: it is very different from the Hudson Bay craters. So which one is correct? Before listing the solution, let's take a look again at the problems of the comet impact theory:

- The effects were global, and in some cases, worse in Siberia
- If the event causes the YDE, it can't also be the end of it, you need a separate mega event
- If the comet is too powerful, it will destroy everything, and if too weak, it will cause extinctions only nearest to the strike site
- The extinctions are far too selective, including in particular megafauna (and the Step Potential explains this because the greater the foot spread, the higher the SP current.)
- The extinctions happened in South America, but if the comet created that kind of dust spread, there should have been extinctions worldwide evenly, and more widespread; instead they are definitely northern hemisphere and Andes mountain oriented.
- Comets can't downthrust whole regions and uplift mountains.³⁵ Some areas uplifted by 4-5 km since 12kya!
- Comets do not prefer one genus over another, or one species over another (such as Grizzlies vs. Short-faced Bear).
- Comet strike in western Greenland cannot create worldwide megatsunami evidence, including errata in Africa going south and in India going north.
- Comets, while part of the story aren't the primary testimony of the most ancient stories; only ONE comet is primary to the Exodus era, and that is the "Great Comet" Venus, whose comet tail has been found³⁶. But the Deluge appears to be a separate event, and perhaps even separate from the more primal Great Flood whose evidence is on the Great Pyramid, in northern Africa, etc...
- Comets cannot produce the kind of crater chains and various aged craters we see at the Carolina Bays, let alone vector changes of impact erata.

The Greenland comet site is large, and it would have been a major event, but the author proposes it was part of a cluster of impacts that were part impact, part electro-comet airburst, such as Tunguska, and that this event may have precipitated the YDE³⁷. The source of the material, the author proposes is the falling satellites pushed upon the Earth by the moon as it passed into the Earth's sway and became trapped. The myths say there were up to 11 satellites (presumably asteroidal) around Earth (Tiamat) at the time that the mysterious "Nibir"³⁸ (Marduk³⁹ or Planet 9⁴⁰) approached.

The author proposes that it was *not* the solar induced event, which happened later when Saturn "died" and gave up Venus, but that the moon itself exchanged prolonged discharges, here presumably with the Earth as the same machined side always faces Earth (in stark contrast to its back side which looks like Mercury) and

³⁵ [3]

³⁶ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/2013JA019164>

³⁷ For a similar event, compare with Jupp's 1491 Melbourne comet which was both a strike creating a 240' wave and an airburst which instantly petrified wood that is found on the beach.

³⁸ Enuma Elish, Tablet 6

³⁹ Perhaps Jupiter but more likely Mars or Mercury, as Marduk was the son of Enki, not Enlil (Jupiter)

⁴⁰ Planet X; could have come from a peel off of the Scholtz Star 70kya; the Book of Enki Tablet 3 makes this a possibility.

since Janus - the two-faced God of Destruction - seems to reflect the “two-faced” behavior of the moon, literally. Also, moon worship has and is considered to be a “sin”, which is the name of the moon: SIN. The moon was also identified with back stabbing wives of the solar god, in many myths.

The author wants to reiterate 3 more facts about the moon:

1. It has water but not plate tectonics. It may indicate the moon was with us during the Saturn flare, and received the affirmed waters⁴¹ during the “Creation of Heaven and Earth” when the “waters separated from the waters (space)”.
2. It does not follow a stable path, as proposed by the Big Whack, and would be expected by mutual accretion with a proto-Tiamat 3+ Gya.
3. The moon’s own tilt (1.5°), despite being electrically attracted to the Earth and facing the same side always, is not the same as Earth’s (23.5°). This is an insurmountable problem for the Accretion Model (AM), as is the first fact. As it stands, Earth’s tilt essentially kills the AM, but as if that isn’t enough, Venus’ rotation is slowing down⁴², thus ending the discussion of AM.

But this isn’t the whole story. In recently declassified documents by the CIA, assertions of polarity shifting related “Continental shift” (ala Hapgood) are said to have been a mechanism for global high winds and mega-tsunamis.⁴³

So how would the poles be shifting both then and now? It is supposed to be a 70-80k year process. This is entirely too soon. And also are there means and evidence for such a shift (other than Atlantis, which the Azores appear to have been, but were downthrust 20-30kya, if dating is correct⁴⁴)?

At this time there isn’t verifiable data, however the author would like to point out that if the moon came in on a north-western to south-easterly vector, and passed over the Earth first in this way, it is entirely possible that the initial thrust of material would create the Hudson Bay and craters, and the Greenland crater, and through uplift of Greenland, drag it along enough to generate mega-tsunamis of the magnitude discussed in the previously mentioned paper by S. Harris (2018),

“In 9577 BC, a satellite of planet Marduk struck somewhere near Ireland and created an earthquake strong enough to liquify a layer of quartz beneath the island of Atlantis west of Ireland. The top half of Atlantis slid west into Rockall Basin for 135 km, then regained friction and broke the lower half free from the continental shelf. Both halves sped across the basin for 225 km until the front edge dug into the basement and brought the split island to a halt. The sea had been raised an average of 1.6 km across Rockall Plateau, the size of Britain. A quarter of the tsunami raced east over Ireland and Britain, thereby extinguishing the megafauna. It raced across Germany and Poland, tore off pieces of the Scandinavian Ice Sheet, crossed the hills of Belarus and flowed around the Ukraine. Now it had a straight path south across flat terrain to the Black Sea, where it arrived at the Bosphorus, a frothy wave 188 m high, moving over 300 kph. Part of the wave filled the basin, and part went over the hills of the Bosphorus, shot into the Aegean Sea, drowned coastal Athens, crossed the Mediterranean Sea and flooded the Egyptian Delta and coastal Levant. The Great Pyramid of Giza retained a high-watermark 133 meters above sea level from runup of this flood. Shellfish found in deep sediment at the base of the Great Pyramid date to 9600 ±300 BC. In central Russia, the Ural Mountains blocked the flood, where it ponded and dropped a bed of silt 500 m above sea level. Further south, a flood with salinity of one third of sea water raised the Caspian Sea to 0 m asl, called the Late Khvalynian Transgression, dated to 10.0 ka BP (9580±17 BC). A simultaneous widespread flood of one-third sea water in the Black Sea is

⁴¹ Literally, Earth came from Saturn, and the water here is of the same isotope as that of the rings of Saturn.

<https://phys.org/news/2018-12-saturn-satellites-earth-moon-phoebe.html>

⁴² <http://sci.esa.int/venus-express/54064-3-spinning-venus-is-slowing-down/>

⁴³ <https://www.cia.gov/library/readingroom/docs/CIA-RDP79B00752A000300070001-8.pdf>

⁴⁴ Interestingly this does match the collapse of Zealandia, as well.

called the Late Drevnechernomorian Transgression. A radiocarbon date of 10.0 ka BP translates to 9580±17BC. (Mertens et al, 2012; Konikov et al., 2007)⁴⁵

Harris produced several graphs as well as equations for calculating the spread of this Great Flood⁴⁶, such as Figure 15:

Figure 15 - Flood levels and ice problems in Antarctica; credit: S. Harris

While the authors disagree upon the exact vector, the direction for both papers (this author and Harris) are in agreement. What Harris does not deal with, however, are the changes in Bolivia such as the tilt angle of the Titicaca shore line, or the Taklamakan seabed, which emptied out into China.

However, both of those events he would likely argue were later events. Still, it is difficult to see how a normal landslide, even one related to a comet would generate the power levels necessary here. Whereas a Velikovskian event would generate kinetic energies into the mega-tera-yotta (10^{39}) of joules transferable

⁴⁵ Ibid. p. 6

⁴⁶ Again, not the Deluge, which was a rainy inundation related to the Saturn Flare event.

somewhat into electrokinetic energies. Because of the charges the bodies would have a difficult time to collide⁴⁷, but would share the energy in brilliant displays of war-like power. Many things would die, and so it would seem to the writers of the Enuma Elish that the Watcher weapon, Kingu, had hovered over the Earth so Marduk could examine the “dead corpse.”⁴⁸

This is, of course, all highly speculative. But the reader should be reminded of the ultimately very thin Earth crust, which would be essentially flimsy when compared with the electrostatic power at hand if the moon passed as close as $\frac{1}{4}$ the distance or closer. The author only proposes $\frac{1}{3}$ the distance, but it could have been close enough for the tidal force of gravity to lift the waves even without impact. The impact may have been merely secondary.

So, looking at the flood maps proposed, it will be difficult to prove much, but it may be possible to explain some of the behaviors of megafauna extinction, in terms of traditional ranges. There are flood maps in the Harris paper, which can be compared, although his focus is upon the European sector because of the excellent evidence of a flood wash extending from the UK towards the Urals, then sloshing south into the Black Sea and back out into the Mediterranean. But look at Figure 9 to see some of the pertinent flood mark heights for the Appalachians:

Figure 16 - Flood Run-ups in Appalachians and along Mississippi River Valley; credit: Harris

⁴⁷ This may explain why a single solitary moon is orbiting pro-grade in Jupiter’s retrograde group:
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.00700.pdf>

⁴⁸ Book of Enki https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xW0ER-DtW_o

It may be that a very, very large landslide could do this. However, it is certainly impossible for a Greenland comet. Notice, however that the flood heights are not sufficient for one thing: total inundation of the Great Plains, where mammoth, mastodon, short-faced bear, dire wolf, American Lion, American Cheetah, etc... made their homes. Applying this data, the author will show a wider spread map:

Figure 17 - Flood Map @ whopping 350 m⁴⁹

Figure 18 - Flood Map @ 'only' 100 m

350 m worldwide seems impossible to the author, and yet even at that such a run-up could not kill all the mammoths interior to the continents, and certainly not even with human help in sparsely populated Siberia. The 100 m level is "thinkable" but it is not tenable. Now some areas did experience higher runup than this tool

⁴⁹ <http://www.floodmap.net/>

can simulate, and those would be heights that could overcome many places: but not the mountainous ranges. Also, humans as a rule did not hunt mammoth or other dangerous megafauna, because of risk of death or injury. The stampede piles found appear to be mostly related to animals escaping the floods and desperate, or even simply pushed off of cliffs. But very, very few kill sites of mammoths with tool marks on bone have ever been found, and it isn't clear this wasn't a lucky scavenging, or a use of an old carcass for tool making purposes. The fact remains, however that human populations were too sparse to compete with megafauna numbers, and this is seen by the fact that even with guns and heavy population, Africa remains strongly covered in megafauna. There is little doubt this isn't because gravity is lower, or that there is less flooding on flat Africa, but that the YDE related event (start or finish) did not hit Africa's savannah interior with the same intensity that it appears to have hit North America and Siberia. Nor has whatever caused the desertification worldwide, stopped Megafauna. The two events appear separate, and what seems to separate them, among other things, is the potential for megafauna **selective** extinction.

Could Greenland have experienced a crustal displacement? It appears that Antarctica could have, but the author will retain, for now, the opinion that the south pole is located at the south pole because it is meant to be. However, the big question is, "why isn't the north pole at the north pole?" Right now the magnetic north pole is racing across the north and is roughly at the actual north pole, but it wasn't before, and neither was Greenland. This seems remarkably unusual and probably has introduced a minor tilt-wobble for the Earth for however long it has been "out of joint". The author does not know. Some evidence seems to suggest that Greenland was formed by the Iceland Hotspot, but this seems backwards. Rather it seems that the hotspot, in this case is actually just a continuation of the mid-Atlantic Ridge, is probably a result of gashing and sudden tearing of the ocean floor, resulting in the sinking of Frisland and Doggerland, and possibly the Azores (Atlantis). So which is the precipitating event? Harris is curiously quiet about this region.

But according to Wang et al... (2018), it does not appear to be in relative motion to the southeast **now**.

Figure 19 - Relative motion (and changes) of the 56 plates; credit: Wang et al...⁵⁰

That doesn't mean it could have moved fast and then been pushed back strongly, by the Eurasian plate. But for now, there is not enough proof for Greenland to have been majorly displaced. So all that remains

⁵⁰ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0012821X18301432>

is the crater strike site, which could not have flooded the world enough, nor selectively killed via nano-dust, the world's certain megafauna on only *some* continents.

The resulting conclusion is therefore back to simplicity: A charged body rotating in a haphazard manner, as it still does, over the Earth, causing massive electric discharges for a brief time during the more chaotic orbit (prior to charge equalization). This charged body dropped errata, shook the Earth, made it groan, and caused massive vajra/thunderbolts which were recorded worldwide with 56 bands or rays coming from a top halo. The event was worldwide, and the thunderbolts were also worldwide. When they struck they precipitated massive step potential currents that targeted large foot-spread megafauna, particularly in North America and Eurasia where the events were strongest. In some places prolonged discharge events - which are not covered in this paper - may have lifted large anode blisters and saturated the ground with more charge and created a higher death toll. It was not a desertifying event, such as the later Saturnian or Venetian black cloud, or Mars red-dust dump (600-700 BCE). It simply killed select species and forced mankind to abandon civilization for 5k-6k years, and bury the Tepe plinths in fear of god-like retribution. This is a reasonable response given the H-bomb level capacities of these vajra. If there was an Atlantis, this effectively ended it, which is not something that would have happened with a simple comet, unless it could end all life. No comet of that capacity has struck since the dinosaur-ending event, which still took several million years to completely die-off. This was a fast die-off, relatively speaking, and it caused mankind to get seriously religious about the gods.

Conclusion

In this paper, three parts addendums to the previously published work have been presented to strengthen the case for plasma-thunderbolts (Vajra) as the cause of the demise of the megafauna. Comparisons of the author's calculations to Dr. Anthony Peratt's were made in light of the discovery of a perfect physical site which matches the description of Dr. Peratt's lab/simulation predictions. Factors for the Gold model were included.

A brief EMF survey was conducted *in situ* at a suspected mound site, but although it showed the expected EMF signatures, other engineering considerations may lead to different (diffusion or technological) conclusions. However, the proximity of the site to the Big Sink location is very suspicious and is not thought to be circumstantial. After all, proximal to this Mt. Horeb site was, once upon a time, a Cosmic Egg/Eye/Womb earthwork, which is no longer extant religiously speaking, but still functions as a way to connect people to the cosmic force (plasma-electromagnetism).

Briefly mentioned were the additions to the discussion of the Greenland impact which very much detracts from the ice impactor hypothesis (Zamora et al.) in Michigan. Numerous faults with that hypothesis were reiterated, and the point was remade about the value of Step Potential as a hitherto undiscussed vector in megafauna extinction models.

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